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**ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS OF NOISE POLLUTION IN THE MANUFACTURING
INDUSTRY*****Ilgar KHURSHUDOV***

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ABSTRACT

The manufacturing industry is a significant contributor to noise pollution, and workers in this industry are at a higher risk of developing hearing loss and other health problems. To combat this issue, the study discussed in the text aims to estimate the maximum working hours for workers exposed to excessive noise levels based on the recommended safe working conditions by NIOSH and OSHA. The study revealed that workers in critical departments are at a higher risk of developing hearing loss due to prolonged exposure to excessive noise levels. To reduce noise pollution in the workplace, employers can implement engineering controls to reduce noise generated by machinery and equipment, limit the duration of exposure to noise levels, rotate workers to minimize exposure, and provide personal protective equipment like earplugs and earmuffs. Employers should prioritize the safety of their workers by providing training on the risks associated with excessive noise exposure and the proper use of personal protective equipment. The study highlights the importance of regular monitoring of noise levels in the workplace and implementing controls to limit exposure to excessive noise levels. Reducing noise pollution in the workplace requires a collaborative approach that involves policymakers, employers, and workers, and it is possible to improve the overall health and productivity of the workforce by implementing effective strategies and controls to reduce the risk of hearing loss and other health problems associated with noise exposure.

Keywords: Noise pollution, evaluation of noise hazards, manufacturing industry.

Introduction

Undesirable or unpleasant sounds are commonly referred to as noise, and its impact on the environment has long been a subject of debate among researchers. Developed countries like Japan, the United Kingdom, and the United States have taken steps to address this problem by implementing legislation. For instance, in 1972, Japan enacted legislation known as the Health and Safety at Work Act, while the United Kingdom introduced the same in 1974 and the United States implemented the Occupational Health & Safety Administration in 1970. In Sweden and Norway, a similar law called the Internal Control Regulation was established. In 1994, the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) in the United States underwent comprehensive updates to cater to a broader range of employees and address new workplace hazards. OSHA now specifies that industrial workers should not be exposed to noise levels exceeding 90 dBA for a duration of 8 hours. These measures demonstrate the recognition of the need to protect workers from excessive noise exposure in order to ensure their well-being.

The human ear and nervous system have their own thresholds for perceiving and accepting sound levels. The impact of noise on individuals depends on factors such as the duration of exposure, the intensity of the noise, and the distance from the noise source, which can affect comfort and the

nervous system. The effects of noise on human health can be classified into four categories: physiological effects (such as high blood pressure, irregular heart rhythms, and ulcers), psychological effects (including stress and irritability), performance effects (resulting in decreased productivity), and physical effects (specifically, hearing loss).

Noise-induced hearing loss is a prevalent form of hearing impairment that occurs when the hair cells in the inner ear (stereocilia) lose their ability to transmit sound information to the brain. This condition is primarily caused by exposure to hazardous noise levels in industrial settings (Rabinowitz P, Galusha D and Slade M. 2006). Furthermore, according to Babisch et al. excessive exposure to noise can lead to physiological cardiovascular effects. (Babisch W, Cardiovascular effects of noise, *Noise & Health*, 2011). Their suggestion is that sudden exposure to loud noise can result in elevated blood pressure, heart rate, and cardiac output due to the release of stress hormones like catecholamine. In a study by Thomas et al. they examined the cardiovascular effects of excessive exposure to environmental noise. (Thomas M, Tommaso G, Babisch W, and Mathias Basner, cardiovascular effects of environmental noise exposure, *Eur. Heart J.* 2014)

The auditory system is sensitive to noise, which not only causes annoyance but also disrupts sleep and impairs cognitive performance. Additionally, epidemiological studies provide evidence that environmental noise is linked to a higher occurrence of conditions such as arterial hypertension, myocardial infarction, and stroke. These studies also suggest that night-time noise, in particular, can disrupt the structure of sleep, trigger vegetative arousals, increase stress hormone levels, and induce oxidative stress. These factors, in turn, may lead to endothelial dysfunction and arterial hypertension.

Numerous studies have been conducted to examine the levels of hazardous noise in various workplaces. Atmaca et al., specifically investigated industrial noise exposure in concrete, iron, cement, and textile factories located in Sivas, Turkey (Atmaca, A., Peker, I. And Atlin, A., Industrial noise and its effects on humans. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies* 2005). The research revealed that the noise levels in all of these industries exceeded 80 dBA, which is considered high. Among employees with 5-10 years of work experience, 74% reported being significantly disturbed by the noise, and this percentage increased to 100% among workers who had been employed for more than 21 years. Furthermore, it is worth noting that the most notable impact of noise is the feeling of discomfort or uneasiness it causes. Studies examining the types of hearing problems indicated that 31% of the employees commonly reported hearing loss, while 35% experienced distress and complications related to noise-induced hearing issues. Nadya et al., conducted a study on occupational noise exposure among toll tellers working at a toll plaza, where they experienced extensive exposure to noise (S. Nadya, Dawal S, Tuan Y and Hamidi M., 2010). The research revealed that the most significant risk came from the peak levels of sound produced by heavy vehicles such as buses and trailers. The excessive noise exposure not only had an impact on their health, including hearing loss, but also caused significant annoyance and job-related difficulties for the toll tellers. The study also highlighted that toll tellers are at risk of being exposed to high levels of noise that exceed threshold limit values. The majority of toll tellers reported being disturbed by the noise sources at the toll plaza, leading to feelings of irritation and discomfort.

Furthermore, the findings from the study by Voorhees et al., on occupational noise hazards revealed that lower noise levels were reported in different tank rooms (Voorhees, J., and Barnes, M.E. 2017). However, the highest noise level recorded was 83.2 dBA, particularly when the pavilion tanks were adjacent to the power washer. Attarchi et al., conducted research on the impact of shift work and individual noise exposure on the incidence of hypertension in the rubber manufacturing industry (Attarchi M, Dehghan F, Safakhah F, Nojomi M, Mohammadi S. 2012). Their study suggested that shift work and prolonged exposure to noise had a protective effect on the occurrence of hypertension. Moreover, Ismail et al., conducted a study on noise level awareness among workers in the quarry industry (Ismail et al., 2013). They emphasized that noise is considered one of the occupational hazards in this industry, and its presence may contribute to a higher prevalence of noise-induced hearing loss.

According to a recent study by Kisku et al., it is recommended that power plants, particularly thermal power plants, should implement precautionary measures and safety protocols to reduce noise levels (Kisku et al., 2006). The researchers conducted noise monitoring using sound level

meters for a duration of 30 minutes at a height of 1.5 meters and a distance of 1 meter, covering 73 locations in small-scale power plants. The study revealed that noise levels exceeding 85 dBA were recorded in control rooms, compressor areas, and fan rooms. Although immediate risks to employees' lives may not be posed by the noise, the researchers concluded that it could lead to neurobehavioral changes, psychological stress, and a general sense of unhappiness in daily life, even in the absence of apparent symptoms of chronic diseases. Thus, mitigating noise in power plants is crucial for the well-being and overall health of the employees. Oyedepo et al., conducted a study that showed no significant difference in the levels of hazardous noise between community and industrial areas (Oyedepo et al., 2009). Their research focused on Ilorin metropolis and revealed that noise pollution levels at 34 out of 47 measuring points exceeded the recommended standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO). This indicates that the city is facing significant environmental noise pollution, with road traffic and industrial machinery identified as the major sources. It is crucial to take steps to address and mitigate this noise pollution in order to safeguard the well-being and quality of life of the residents in Ilorin. In 2015, Anjorin et al., conducted a study which revealed a significant risk of noise-induced hearing loss in manufacturing and processing industries. The research focused on measuring the average noise equivalent level (LAeq) to identify noisy machines and establish baseline data. By utilizing a precision-grade sound level meter over a five-day period at 30-minute intervals, it was observed that the noise limit values exceeded regulatory criteria and international standards in nearly all of the machines assessed. The study also highlighted the inadequacy of noise control measures in the surveyed industries, emphasizing the urgent need for improved interventions to safeguard the hearing health of workers.

This study aimed to examine the levels of noise pollution in various departments of a manufacturing industry. The findings from this research are valuable for increasing awareness among workers regarding noise exposure and assisting industry management in implementing effective mitigation strategies. The study followed the guidelines provided by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) and the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) for data collection and experimental procedures. By adhering to these guidelines, the study ensured a reliable and standardized approach to assessing noise pollution in the manufacturing industry.

Materials and Methods

A Sound Level Meter (SLM) is a device used to measure the level of noise in units of decibels (dBA). In this study, the Impulse Integrating Sound Meter model Quest SoundPro SP SE-2SLM was chosen, which has the capability to capture readings in both fast and slow modes. The SLM records the sound pressure level during a specific time period. When sound waves reach the SLM, the vibrations from the waves cause small air molecules to impact the surface of the microphone. This mechanical energy is then transformed into an electrical signal, which is displayed as a sound value in decibels (dBA).

To ensure consistent and accurate readings, the CASELLA Calibration model was employed for each measurement sequence. This calibration is essential for compliance with noise exposure standards specified by regulations such as the Noise at Work regulations and environmental noise regulations. The data collected from the QUEST Soundpro SP SE-2 during area sound monitoring activities were transferred to a computer using the 3M™ Detection Management Software (DMS). The collected data were then analyzed based on the corresponding constant sound pressure level (Leq) and peak sound pressure level (SPL). Octave band data, including both one-third and full-octave bands, were recorded for Leq at each location during the selected events or periods of measurement.

Figure 1 illustrates the arrangement of the Sound Level Meter (SLM) and calibrator used in the study. These devices were placed in four specific areas of the manufacturing facility known to have potential noise hazards: the polishing site, surface treatment site, CAM & CNC machine area, and quality control area. The monitoring was conducted consistently over a period of seven days, with measurements taken for 8 hours each day. The factory operated with three shifts per day, each consisting of 8 hours. The SLMs were positioned in a stationary manner near the noise sources, at an estimated height of 1 meter.

Sound Level M		Integrating Sound Level Meter. Made	: QUEST
Model			: SoundPro SP SE-2 (JKKP PSLM 50/06)
Serial No			: BA109005

(a)

Calibrator-Made : (		: CEL-110/2	
Serial No			049113

(b)

Figure 1 Noise monitoring (a) SLM and (b) calibrator devices

Findings and Discussion

The noise level in the Polishing Department was measured over a two-day period, from 7am to 4pm. The recorded data shows that the highest noise peaks occurred at 8:30am and 3:30pm on both days. Additionally, there was a peak noise level recorded at 12:00pm on Tuesday. These peak values exceeded 90 dBA, indicating a significant level of noise. It is worth noting that the primary source of annoyance during these times was the communication between operators and the noise generated by the polishing machines. The results indicate that on Monday, the noise levels consistently exceeded 85 dBA for approximately 14% of the monitoring period. Similarly, on Tuesday, the noise levels exceeded 85 dBA for approximately 27% of the monitoring period.

The results display the noise level (dBA) over time at the Surface Treatment department. The measurements were taken daily from 8am to 5pm for a week. It was observed that the noise level consistently peaked at 90 dBA around 8:30 am each day, while the average noise level throughout the week was approximately 76 dBA. Although the noise levels in this department were not as severe compared to other areas, approximately 5% of the time exceeded the threshold of 85 dBA. The results indicate that the noise generated by the surface treatment machines often exceeded 65 dBA, causing interruptions in normal conversations between operators, particularly those working in this section. This highlights the need for measures to mitigate the noise levels and ensure a conducive working environment for the operators.

The CAM & CNC area in the factory poses a high-risk noise exposure. Figure 1 illustrates the noise readings recorded in this area, with an average level of 103.27 dBA, surpassing the allowable limits set by NIOSH and OSHA. The noise levels exhibit fluctuations both on a daily and hourly basis. Thursday and Friday recorded the highest noise levels at 120 dBA, while Monday had the lowest values. On an hourly basis, the maximum sound level readings were observed in the early morning, gradually decreasing towards the afternoon. However, the noise levels significantly increased again in the afternoon and decreased towards the end of the shift. Several factors contribute to the sound level variations in this area. It is anticipated that the full operation of machines in the early morning, along with other production activities such as conveyor movement and material handling, contribute to higher

noise levels. This excessive noise poses a potential harm to the workers in this area, necessitating the factory management to pay special attention and implement measures to mitigate the noise risks.

Figure 1 Daily and hourly noise level at CAM & CNC area

The hourly-average noise levels were calculated for all departments throughout the study period. Figure 2 presents the average noise levels recorded in each department. It is evident that the CNC & CAM area had the highest noise levels compared to the other departments. The hourly readings in this area ranged from 90 dBA to 120 dBA, exceeding the allowable limits recommended by NIOSH and OSHA. Similar noise levels were observed in the other departments, with their noise levels ranging from 62 dBA to 90 dBA, which fell within the permissible limits. These findings highlight the need for immediate attention and mitigation strategies in the CNC & CAM area to ensure the safety and well-being of the workers exposed to high noise levels.

Figure 2 Hourly-average noise level for all departments on Saturday

Evaluation of Noise Exposure and Duration of Work Shift

To assess the shift exposure in accordance with the recommendations of NIOSH and OSHA, it is necessary to calculate the actual noise exposure (L_{EX}) and noise dose. L_{EX} represents the noise energy level averaged over an 8-hour period and is closely related to the L_{eq} (equivalent steady sound level averaged over time). Equation 1 can be used to measure these values (Workers compensation board of British Columbia, 2007).

$$L_{EX} = L_{eq} + \text{correction for the shift length} \quad (1)$$

where the correction is given by the **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 Shift time correction to measure L_{EX}

Table 1 presents a comparison of the noise levels measured in accordance with the NIOSH (1998) and OSHA (1983) guidelines. The L_{EX} values were calculated based on an 8 hours/day and 5 days/week work pattern. The noise dose was determined using interpolation and the nomograph provided in Appendix 1 of WorkSafeBC (*Workers compensation board of British Columbia, 2007*). The results indicate that the permissible working hours for CAM and CNC per shift should be less than 0.125 and 1.33 hours respectively, based on the NIOSH and OSHA guidelines. It is evident from Table 1 that the noise exposure in these departments exceeds the permissible levels by a significant margin, with noise dose levels being 64 times and 6300% higher than the permissible limits. On the other hand, the other departments have permissible working hours exceeding 8 hours per shift.

Table 1 The comparison of noise level with NIOSH (1998) and OSHA (1983) guidelines

Department	L_{eq} (dBA)	L_{EX} (dBA)	Noise Dose (%)	Permitted Shift Length (hr)/(day) (NIOSH)	Permitted Shift Length (hr)/(day) (OSHA)
Polishing	77.97	77.97	20	>8 hours	>8 hours
CAM & CNC	103.27	103.27	6300	0.125 hours	1.33 hours
Quality Control	77.10	77.10	16	>8 hours	>8 hours
Surface Treatment	76.67	76.67	15	>8 hours	>8 hours

Conclusion and Recommendations

The noise survey conducted in the manufacturing factory has revealed that the noise levels exceed the permissible exposure limit set by NIOSH and OSHA regulations. As a result, it is necessary for the management to take remedial action. The CAM & CNC department recorded the highest noise level, averaging at 103.27 dBA. While the other departments are permitted to operate for more than 8 hours per shift, the CAM & CNC department is limited to 1.33 hours per shift in order to mitigate the risk of hearing impairment. To minimize noise exposure, the employer should provide earplugs or earmuffs to the respective departments as additional control measures in the factory.

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